

ASSESSING ON MATHEMATICS LEARNING MATERIALS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MATHEMATICAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Educational practices shifted due to the challenges brought by COVID-19, flexible learning was adopted and most public schools used modular learning modality as a learning contingency plan for the student's academic development. Department of Education is in progress to ensure the quality of learning materials to be given to the students, in line with this, this study aimed to assess the satisfaction with Mathematics learning materials and attitude towards mathematical development of Grade 8 students. The study used descriptive and correlational research design in conducting the study. This focused on assessing the satisfaction with Mathematics learning materials and determining the perceived attitude towards mathematical development of the students. The result of the study revealed that the respondents assessed the learning materials in terms of general quality as with high quality, in terms of didactic adaptation as with high level and has the ability to motivate. Likewise, the findings show that the respondents perceived the attitude towards mathematical development in terms of interest in Mathematics, anxiety towards Mathematics, self-efficacy, extrinsic motivation, self-concept, usefulness, and value as high. Moreover, a positive significant relationship was found between the assessed satisfaction on Mathematics learning materials and the attitude toward Mathematical development. Furthermore, the findings also revealed that the implication and contribution to learning *as* parameters on assessed satisfaction on Mathematics learning materials singly or in combination predict the attitude towards Mathematical development. *Thus*, this study recommends the learning materials developers should consider the implication and contribution to learning of the material to ensure a high standard of instructional delivery to attain total learning developments of the students.

Keywords: Mathematics Learning Materials, Mathematical Development